

PUPIL-SCIENCE TOOLBOX

Tools and activities for growing
young Citizen Scientists

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Introduction

MEET (*Missions: Engagement and Education for Tomorrow*) is a project funded by the European Commission that aims to enhance the academic excellence of Milan, promote culture and foster scientific citizenship by providing accurate information to the general public. The MEET project consortium features the five main universities in Milan (Università degli Studi di Milano-Bicocca, Università degli Studi di Milano, Politecnico di Milano, Università Commerciale Luigi Bocconi, Università Vita-Salute San Raffaele) and a science communication agency (formicablu), plus, as associated partners, two institutional actors (Comune di Milano and Regione Lombardia) and a cooperative company created within the NextGenerationEU that fosters the cooperation between universities and industries (MUSA). The project is divided into two intertwined sub-projects: the first, **MEETmeTONIGHT**, is the official event of the European Night of Researchers, for the 2024 and 2025 editions. The night events combine different types of participatory activities, such as talks, stands, workshops. The second program, **MEETme@School**, is dedicated to schools of all levels and provides for direct meetings between students, teachers, researchers and researchers. Università Vita-Salute San Raffaele is coordinator of all the activities with the schools with a leading role in the initiatives connected with the Citizen Science approach. Through *Citizen Science* activities, the project promotes a research-oriented teaching approach and a more open, sustainable and inclusive vision of science. Engaging in scientific projects will enhance students' active participation in their learning, while teachers will gain opportunities for professional growth by collaborating directly with experts in the field.

An objective of MEETme@School was to create a "**Pupil Science Toolbox**" that provides an archive of educational resources to support teachers to include Citizen Science in schools. The contents will include a wide range of open-access materials - didactic slides, methodological guides and explanatory sheets - designed to facilitate the teaching of research techniques in an accessible and interactive way. In addition, it will offer guidelines to help teachers integrate these materials into their teaching plans, ensuring that scientific inquiry becomes a regular and meaningful part of the school curriculum.

One of the most valuable aspects of the toolbox is its open-access nature. By making these resources available for free, we aim to democratize access to scientific knowledge, allowing educators from different regions and contexts to benefit from the materials. This not only improves the scope of the project but also ensures that students from different educational backgrounds can interact with the same high-quality tools for learning and experimentation.

Lasting impact is a key objective. By creating the toolbox as a long-term educational resource, we wish to ensure that its benefits extend far beyond the project. Even after the project ends, schools will continue to have access to the materials, allowing future generations of students to engage in scientific research. and teachers to integrate the materials into their curriculum planning.

In summary, the "Pupil Sciences" program is an innovative approach to make scientific research accessible to the younger generation, with a focus on promoting lifelong skills in critical thinking and inquiry.

What is Citizen Science?

How can we help people to properly inform themselves, understand and face collective choices in full awareness? Are science, involvement, and bottom-up participation reconcilable ideas?

The recent pandemic highlighted a growing tension between public trust and distrust in science: now more than ever we need correct and reliable scientific communication, and to find a common ground between the scientists and the public to increase their awareness of the scientific method and their involvement in collective choices.

Moreover, several global crises are now posing a challenge to all societies around the world, but “*there are scientific recommendations, but no social consensus for implementation*”¹: the loss of biodiversity, climate change, and emerging zoonotic diseases need **the commitment and efforts of everyone**, policymakers, industry, science, and civil society included, to ensure healthy and resilient societies.

The connection between science and society is therefore an increasingly crucial factor for a democratic development that allows citizens to make the proper choices for their lives and for the society itself. *Citizen Science* or “**science made by citizens**” can help citizens understand and share not only the meaning and the value of scientific research, but also its effects in everyday life and for a good standard of living, especially when applied to the local context in which citizens live. Citizen Science is therefore **a tool** that can connect different spheres of society and **a bona fide scientific methodology** that, when done correctly, has the potential to influence important policy decisions.

The **definition of Citizen Science** given by the European Commission is ²:

Fig. 1 - Definition of Citizen Science given by the European Commission²

1. European Commission (2022), The transformative potential of Citizen Science, Magazine of European Research Council, <https://erc.europa.eu/news-events/magazine-article/transformative-potential-citizen-science>

2. Directorate-General for Research and Innovation - European Commission Citizen Science, 2020, Elevating research and innovation through societal engagement, <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d1768147-f17a-11ea-991b-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-152465380>

In parallel with the process of democratisation of science, Citizen Science plays a revolutionary role in disrupting the *ivory tower paradigm*, that posits that true knowledge can be achieved only in research institutes or universities. This paradigm is reductive and not inclusive, failing to recognize that many usable notions are available outside the academia. The process of accepting the value of Citizen Science is still in progress, but scientists are finally recognizing its importance and benefits. The *conditio sine qua non* for a Citizen Science project is therefore that researchers exercise a certain degree of “humility” to step back and learn from others, resulting in a mutually beneficial relationship between science and society.

Citizen Science isn't just a buzzword...

It's a movement, a collaboration between passionate individuals, coming together to contribute knowledge, skills, and curiosity to scientific endeavours

It's about harnessing the power of collective intelligence to solve real-world problems.

Citizen Science has the potential to revolutionize how we approach scientific discovery, making it more inclusive, diverse, and impactful

Responsible Research & Innovation (RRI) pillars

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) engages public and accountable stakeholders to achieve research and innovation results that are:

- ethically acceptable
- sustainable
- socially desirable

The rationale behind RRI is that science and technology have the potential to change the future, but this can happen if citizens, industry, and other societal stakeholders are involved in the process.

RRI is based on the following 6 pillars: Public Engagement, Open Science, Research Integrity and Ethics, Science education, Gender equality, and Governance (Figure 2)³. Accordingly, core principles for responsibly conducting research and innovation are anticipation, reflexivity, inclusion, responsiveness, openness, and transparency.

Fig. 2 - Six pillars of RRI

3. D.-G. for R. and I. European Commission, Responsible research and innovation: Europe's ability to respond to societal challenges, (2014). <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/2be36f74-b490-409e-bb60-12fd438100fe/language-en/format-PDF/source-search>

Citizen Science is positioned at the interface between Public Engagement and Open Science (Figure 2), but it can also incorporate all 6 dimensions of RRI ⁴:

Public Engagement, engaging citizens and other stakeholders to collaborate within the research and innovation ecosystem and tackle societal challenges

Open Science, making science accessible and unrestricted

Integrity and ethics of research, linking research to the 10 principles of Citizen Science and considering related ethical issues

Gender equality, promoting gender balance and the inclusion of gender and sex issues in research and Innovation, and all participatory activities, including communication used to engage women

Science education, encouraging scientific literacy and critical thinking, and promoting STEAM (Science Technology Engineering Art and Maths) careers

Governance, fostering liaisons with legislators to encourage official use of citizen-generated data and evidence-based policies

4. Adapted from Rosa Arias, *The Citizen Science Funding Landscape*, TIME4CS webinar 9.3.23

Ten principles of Citizen Science

In 2015 the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) drafted the *10 principles of Citizen Science*⁵, with the aim of finding common aspects and guidelines valid for all initiatives and these ten principles have been translated into the 27 languages of the European Union, to give them the greatest possible dissemination.

Here the 10 principles:

Fig. 3 – Ten principles of Citizen Science

5. European Citizen Science Association, 2015, *Ten Principles of Citizen Science*, <http://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/XPR2N>

How many Citizen Science projects?

The forms of Citizen Science that we see today are very different from the past. In fact, it is now an activity that can be **carried out by everyone**, whereas once it was only for few interested individuals⁶. From the initial collaborative role in data collection, citizens have now also participated in the formulation of research questions, the creation of methods and the analysis of the data themselves⁷. The ways in which citizens participate in projects can be varied: some make their own local resources available (such as, for example, their backyard), others share the computational resources of their PCs, and still others provide their cognitive skills in data analysis.

Citizen Science has spread in recent years mainly due to advances in technology, particularly the Internet and mobile devices as these tools have made it easy for people to contribute using specific Apps and share their observations⁸ generating data that would otherwise be difficult or expensive to obtain⁹.

6. Silvertown, J. (2009) *A new dawn for Citizen Science*. Trends in Ecology, Evolution 24(9): 467-471, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2009.03.017>.

7. Cooper, C.B., Lewenstein, B.V. (2016) *Two meanings of Citizen Science*. in Cavalier, D., Kennedy E.B. (Eds.) *The Rightful Place of Science: Citizen science*, pp. 51-62, AZ: Consortium for Science, Policy, Outcomes, Tempe

8. Newman, G., Wiggins, A., Crall, A., Graham, G., Newman, S., Crowston, K. (2012) *The future of Citizen Science: Emerging technologies and shifting paradigms*, Front Ecol Environment 6(10): 298-304. <https://doi.org/10.1890/110294>.

9. Cohn, J.P. (2008) *Citizen science: Can Volunteers Do Real Research?*, BioScience 58(3): 192-197. <https://doi.org/10.1641/B580303>

Citizen Science projects can therefore be classified according to **volunteer engagement**¹⁰ (Figure 4), usually paralleled by a decrease in the leadership and control played on the project by the “professional” researchers.

Fig. 4 - Level of citizen and scientist involvement

According to the type of project, not only can the percentage of volunteer engagement vary, but also which kind of data is collected ¹¹ (Figure 5).

10. Haklay, M. (2013) *Citizen Science and Volunteered Geographic Information: Overview and Typology of Participation*, Crowdsourcing Geogr. Knowl., Springer Netherlands, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-4587-2_7

11. Pocock, M.J.O., Chapman, D.S., Sheppard, L.J. & Roy, H.E. (2014). *Choosing and Using Citizen Science: a guide to when and how to use citizen science to monitor biodiversity and the environment*. Centre for Ecology & Hydrology https://www.ceh.ac.uk/sites/default/files/sepa_choosingandusingcitizenscience_interactive_4web_final_amended-blue1.pdf

Obviously, the more people participate, the more accurate the data will be, corroborating the chances of an accurate answer to the scientific problem investigated and reducing the probability of biased observations. Moreover, a vast amount of data can be collected in a shorter time.

A well-constructed protocol for the project is of utmost importance: Citizen Science is a scientific approach like any other and therefore it is at its best when it is specific, that is, when the question to be addressed is clear¹⁵. In this way citizens or students can collect data of comparable quality to the data collected by professionals¹²⁻¹³.

Fig. 5 - Collection of data in Citizen Science projects

12. Crall, A. W., Newman, G. J., Stohlgren, T. J., Holfelder, K. A., Graham, J., & Waller, D. M. (2011). *Assessing citizen science data quality: An invasive species case study*. *Conservation Letters*, 4(6), 433–442. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1755-263X.2011.00196.x>

13. Lewandowski, E., Caldwell, W., Elmquist, D., & Oberhauser, K. (2017). *Public Perceptions of Citizen Science*. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 2(1), 3. <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.77>

Why Citizen Science in Europe?

Citizen Science is gaining more and more ground in Europe, with projects paying special attention to environmental issues. A recent study¹⁴ provides interesting data on this growing trend. The study analysed 157 Citizen Science projects in Europe participating in the Horizon 2020 program, mainly from Spain (37%), Portugal (17%) and Italy (11%). The results show that most projects focus on environment and land issues (66.5%), with a particular focus on biodiversity (35.6%).

European Commission contributes to foster and finance Citizens Science projects¹⁵ because they are characterized by:

Excellence:

- Broadening the scope of research and innovation and the quality and quantity of data collected, discussed and analysed
- Increasing the robustness of results
- Enabling innovative and creative approaches
- Harnessing collective intelligence (often excluded from contributing to Research & Innovation)

Effectiveness:

- Aligning results with society's needs, values and expectations, ensuring greater relevance and adoption
- Reducing time-to-market for innovative products and services
- Triggering behavioural changes

Rise in society's trust in science

- Increasing openness, transparency and 'co-ownership' of society
- Often leading to more inclusive outcomes
- Encouraging mutual learning between science and society

14. Giardullo, P., Neresini, F., Marín-González, E., Luís, C., Magalhães, J. and Arias, R. (2023). *Citizen Science and participatory science communication: an empirically informed discussion connecting research and theory*, Journal of Science Communication, <https://doi.org/10.22323/2.22020201>

15. Farrer, L, Delaney N., 27-10-2021, *Citizen and societal engagement: A policy and programme priority for the European Commission*, EU-Citizen Science event, <https://eu-citizen.science/static/site/files/Citizen%20and%20societal%20engagement%20-%20Niamh%20Delaney%20and%20Linden%20Farrer.pdf>

Three main reasons for embracing Citizen Science in your teaching

1. Citizen Science offers new educational perspectives

Students can develop a greater interest in science, collecting meaningful, real-world data and improving their understanding of the scientific method. Moreover, on one side students may offer different perspectives from adult scientists and being involved in a Citizen Science project can help them understand new way of thinking about problems; on the other side scientists could make use of data collected by students to study real problems.

With Citizen Science everybody is rewarded: **citizens become researchers and researchers increase their sense of citizenship.**

2. Citizen Science helps the development of cross-cutting practices in schools

The sense of control and responsibility that participants assume during the project for oneself and for the environment involved. It is strengthened both by the collaborative approaches used in Citizen Science and the addressing of community problems of a project

The collaborative process in which multiple actors (citizens, stakeholders, researchers) use methods and tools for working together without a hierarchical scale

Transformations that invest communities and in a wider range cultures and institutions. It leads to a change also in attitudes, values and consciousness

Increase in the transparency of data, protocols and actions

3. Citizen Science goes beyond outreach and Public Engagement

As the first of the 10 principles of Citizen Science goes, *Citizen Science projects actively engage citizens in scientific activities that generate new knowledge or understanding.* While Public Engagement initiatives also actively engage citizens in scientific activities, Citizen Science activities actually generate new knowledge or understanding. As mentioned above, Citizen Science is a de facto research methodology. Just like any other one therefore, it has advantages and limitations: in a research laboratory, all conditions are controlled, which allows causal conclusions to be drawn.

In the real world, we can reach communities that would probably never come in the laboratory. The strength lies in the combination of methods, where the limitations of one method can be offset by the advantages of another ¹⁶.

Project Based Learning and Citizen Science

Citizen Science is a valuable teaching tool that enables students to become aware of many current issues, to understand the value of participating in a community for the common good¹⁷, but most importantly to affect **the meaning of disciplinary content**, often learned in school in a de-contextualized way.

Citizen Science shares many features with **Project-Based Learning (PBL)**¹⁸, a teaching method in which students can face real-world problems, growing up in their critical thinking skill. Meaningful projects for the community are the common ground where Citizen Science in schools and teaching methodologies meet.

The theoretical background of Project-Based Learning is characterized by four major driving ideas:

1. **Active construction:** students are pushed to construct their knowledge in real-world activities similar to those that experts live daily and to solve problems.
2. **Situated learning:** students experience phenomena throughout the implementation of a PBL project by designing investigations, explaining, modelling, and presenting their ideas to others. As a result, students can understand the link between new information acquired during the data collection, what was known before the data collection, and the conceptual framing of the inquiry.
3. **Social interactions:** students share and debate with others on the issue identified in the project, creating a sense of community of learners.
4. **Cognitive tools:** students acquire new skills related to technologies usually used by scientists and that are specific for the collection of scientific data, visualization and data analysis, planning and testing models, developing documents and infographics to share results and disseminate.

A Project-Based Classroom allows therefore students to investigate questions, following the inquiry method of scientists: proposing hypotheses and discussing how something can be tested and improved. This process results in the acquisition or corroboration of soft skills, such as: team building and working together, facing uncertain situations, seeking new ways out of comfort zone, acceptance of mistakes and failures as part of the process needed to ameliorate in the future.

16. Crone, E., 2022, *Knowledge is everywhere*, European Research Council Magazine, <https://erc.europa.eu/news-events/magazine-article/knowledge-everywhere>

17. Shah, H.R., Martinez, L.R. (2016). Current Approaches in Implementing Citizen Science in the Classroom. Journal of Microbiology, Biology Education, <https://doi.org/10.1128/jmbe.v17i1.1032>

18. Adapted from Citizen Science in the Classroom: A toolkit, an online course on <https://moodle.eu-citizen.science/course/view.php?id=35>

The correspondence between Citizen Science steps and the features of PBL is as follows (Figure 6)¹⁹:

Citizen Science	Project-Based Learning	Cross-cutting principles
<p>Scoping activities to help map issues of interest and the work that has been done before</p>	<p>A driving question is set that students explore. As are result, they learn and apply important ideas in the discipline</p>	<p>Empowerment, co-creation</p>
<p>The planning stage is directly focused on preparing the community for data collection</p>	<p>Students, teachers and community members, engage in collaborative activities – to find solutions to the driving questions</p>	<p>Empowerment, co-creation</p>
<p>Sensing to gather information about the issue</p>	<p>Learning technologies to help students to participate in activities that are normally beyond their ability</p>	<p>Co-creation</p>
<p>Consideration of the community’s awareness understanding of the have and they data</p>	<p>Inquiry process with a continuous refinement process, collection of feedback from peers and experts (under teacher's guidance)</p>	<p>Empowerment, Change-making</p>
<p>If more activities are planned in the future, it is important to reflect on what worked well</p>	<p>Use and reflect on the information given by students to adjust the content and process for the next project implementation</p>	<p>Empowerment, Change-making</p>
<p>The legacy refers to the impact of the work, and how for reaching it will be</p>	<p>Students create a set of shared assets that address the driving question</p>	<p>Openess</p>

Fig. 6 – The parallels between Citizen Science and Project based-learning

19. Krajcik JS, Blumenfeld PC. Project Based Learning (2014), The Cambridge Handbook of the Learning Sciences. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139519526.018>

What are the advantages of participating in a Citizen Science project?

For students

- Increasing trust in science and expert opinions
- Expressing their views on the development of scientific projects
- Improving their understanding of the scientific method
- Offering a new way of thinking about problems
- Improving critical thinking and fight misinformation and disinformation

For researchers

- Understanding what people really care about
- Recognizing the impact their work has or should have in society
- Increasing transparency of project organization and data
- Involving volunteers from the beginning in the co-design of the research

Fig. 7 - List of advantages for students and researchers in participating in a Citizen Science project

Useful tools

Below is a list of tools that can be used by everyone to make activities more engaging and pluralistic.

To analyse and visualize data in other devices:

- [Google sheets](#)
- [Data Wrapper](#)
- [Canva](#)

Click the links

To collect feedback, co-create, collaborate and stimulate criticism:

- [Miroboard](#)
- [Padlet](#)
- [Mural](#)
- [Mentimeter](#)
- [Slido](#)
- [Wooclap](#)

Databases of Citizen Science projects:

- [SciStarter](#)
- [Zooniverse](#)
- [European Citizen Science Platform](#)
- [Citizen Science Italia \(CSI\)](#)

Examples of citizen science projects:

- [StallCatchers](#)
- [Stomycraft](#)
- [Colony B](#)
- [Eyewire](#)
- [EteRNA](#)
- [Globe at Night](#)
- [Foldscope](#)
- [GLOBE Clouds](#)
- [Sourdough for Science](#)
- [ESA IMPACT](#)

Fig. 8 - List of tools

To analyse and visualize data in other devices

- **Google sheets** is a free, web-based spreadsheet program, offered by Google that allows users to create, edit and organize data collaboratively and in real-time²⁰.
- **Datawrapper** is an online tool which enables the development of the data in beautiful charts, maps or tables with a few clicks²¹.
- **Canva** is an online design tool that helps beginners perfect their design skills by proposing, for example, templates of Power Point presentations, flyers, posters...etc²².

To collect feedback, co-create, collaborate and stimulate criticism

- **Miroboard** is a collaborative digital whiteboard designed to create and share interactive workspaces in real-time. You can create new boards, which can be blank or based on predefined templates. It is possible to add various elements such as sticky notes, text, shapes, images and documents²³.
- **Padlet** is an online interactive platform that works as a virtual post board with a simple and user-friendly interface that promotes active, creative, and collaborative learning²⁴.
- **Mural** is a visual whiteboard that facilitates more collaborative and innovative hybrid remote teamwork²⁵.
- **Mentimeter** is a web-based platform that enables to create interactive presentations with real-time input from the audience²⁶.
- **Slido** is an easy-to-use Q&A and polling platform. It helps people to get the most out of meetings and events by bridging the gap between speakers and their audiences²⁷.
- **Wooclap** is an interactive online platform that allows teachers and educators to create engaging and interactive quizzes and polls²⁸.

20. <https://workspace.google.com/intl/it/products/sheets/>

21. <https://www.datawrapper.de/>

22. <https://www.canva.com/graphs/>

23. <https://miro.com/>

24. <https://padlet.com/>

25. <https://www.mural.co/>

26. <https://www.mentimeter.com/>

27. <https://www.slido.com/>

28. <https://www.wooclap.com/>

Databases of Citizen Science projects

- **Citizenscience.eu** is an online platform for sharing knowledge, tools, training and resources for citizen science – by the community, for the community²⁹.
- **Citizen Science Italia** is a national network of initiatives, experts, universities, research centers, scientific museums, associations and Italian public bodies, which aim to build inclusive and collaborative tools and solutions, in an open science perspective, in close contact with the other international networks³⁰.
- **SciStarter** is a globally acclaimed online citizen science hub where thousands of projects, searchable by location, topic, age level, etc., have been registered by individual project leaders or imported through partnerships with federal governments, NGOs, and universities³¹.
- **Zooniverse** is a citizen science web portal owned and operated by the Citizen Science Alliance. It hosts some of the largest, most popular, and most successful citizen science projects on the Internet³².

Example of Citizen Science projects at school

Here is a list of Citizen Science projects selected by the MMS teams suitable for pupils:

- **StallCatchers** is an online game suitable for everyone from 6 to 99 years old. In the game, you look at movies from the brains of mice and try to identify vessels as flowing or stalled. This helps to speed up Alzheimer's disease research at Cornell University: in 1 hour of gaming the community of StallCatchers can produce the same amount of data that requires a researcher 5 days in the lab³³.
- **Stomycraft** is a video game, developed by Federazione delle Associazioni Incontinenti e Stomizzati (FAIS, the Italian federation of incontinent and ostomised people), that teaches ostomised children to manage the ostomy pouch while facing enemies and building new worlds. They participate in various challenges with their caregiver and cultivate mutual trust together. Moreover, they can play with people from all over the world, meet new friends and safely share doubts³⁴.
- **Colony B** is a puzzle mobile game developed at McGill University in which players are in charge of growing a colony of bacteria, which accumulate to survive. The goal is to identify clusters of bacteria that are accumulating: clusters generate points based on their density and allow in turn to grow the players' colonies. The results are used to analyze data from the American Gut Project based at the University of California San Diego³⁵.

29. <https://citizenscience.eu/projects>

30. <https://www.citizenscience.it/>

31. <https://scistarter.org/>

32. <https://www.zooniverse.org/>

33. <https://stallcatchers.com/>

34. <https://stomycraft.org/>

35. <http://csb.cs.mcgill.ca/colonyb/>

- **Eyewire** is a game to map the brain. Hundreds of thousands of people from around the world, with no need for a scientific background, are mapping the 3D structure of neurons and advancing the quest to understand ourselves³⁶.
- **EteRNA** is a browser-based “game with a purpose” that lets players solve puzzles related to the folding of RNA molecules. The goal is to help find RNA molecules that are biologically active³⁷.
- **Globe at Night** is an international Citizen Science campaign, developed by NASA, to raise public awareness of the impact of light pollution by inviting Citizen Scientists to measure & submit their night sky brightness observations³⁸.
- **Foldscope** is a paper microscope that combines low-cost materials with precision optics. This innovation results in microscopes that are both high-quality and affordable. The microscopes have a range of magnifications (50X-340X), allowing the visualization of tiny microorganisms to larger samples like insects, plants, fabrics, and tissues. Foldscope can also attach to mobile phones for imaging and is very portable, durable, and waterproof³⁹.
- **GLOBE Clouds** is an app-based tool, sponsored by NASA, which will help the Citizen Scientists document what they see in the sky. Through the GLOBE Observer app, they can report on overall cloud cover and surface conditions that can impact satellite observations, cloud types, cloud opacity, sky conditions and visibility, and they can upload photos of what they see in the sky⁴⁰.
- **Sourdough for Science** is a project in which Citizen Scientists create a sourdough starter by mixing flour and water, then track its growth over two weeks by measuring its height and pH. By participating, they contribute their data to a larger scientific study, helping to uncover how different flours impact microbial growth and, ultimately, the flavour and texture of the bread. Additional modules include exploring variables that influence starter growth, graphing collected data, and learning about common sourdough microbes⁴¹.
- **ESA IMPACT** is an immersive sci-fi game set on the Moon, in which players build and manage a lunar base, generating valuable scientific data along the way. They analyse and annotate craters on actual satellite images of the moon, aiding the European Space Agency (ESA) in mapping the lunar surface, and potentially assisting in future moon landings and research⁴².

36. <https://eyewire.org/explore>

37. <https://www.citizenscience.gov/eterna/#>

38. <https://globeatnight.org/>

39. <https://foldscope.com/>

40. <https://observer.globe.gov/>

41. <http://studentsdiscover.org/lesson/sourdough-for-science/>

42. <https://blogs.esa.int/exploration/gaming-to-the-moon/>

Teacher Perspectives and Challenges

A recent study explored teacher knowledge, experience, and interest in incorporating Citizen Science into their teaching⁴³. The research involved a **questionnaire** completed by 355 primary and secondary **school teachers** across Australia, highlighting on the role of Citizen Science in education.

The results were encouraging: over half of the teachers were familiar with the concept of Citizen Science, and about 40% had already introduced such projects in their classrooms. These initiatives often included activities like environmental data collection, naturalistic observations and participation in genuine scientific research - earning positive feedback for their engagement and impact.

However, despite its potential, introduction of Citizen Science into classrooms, presents notable challenges. Teachers pointed to gaps in knowledge, limited time and a lack of confidence, alongside concerns about aligning Citizen Science projects with the national curriculum.

Interestingly, 92% of respondents indicated that **curriculum-aligned projects** would motivate them to adopt Citizen Science more widely in their classrooms. To ensure that Citizen Science evolves beyond being a sporadic activity, it must seamlessly integrate with local school curriculums. This guarantees its sustained relevance and effectiveness in student learning experiences.

43. Braz Sousa L, Kenneally C, Golumbic Y, Martin JM, Preston C, Rutledge P, et al. (2024) *Teacher experiences and understanding of citizen science in Australian classrooms*. PLoS OE 19(11): e0312680. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0312680>

The six phases for Citizen Science implementation in schools

There are **six main phases**⁴⁴ that can be identified and are distinguished by timing, duration, main actors involved, and objectives (figure 7): 1) Definition of scope; 2) Planning; 3) Sensing or data collection; 4) Awareness; 5) Reflections; 6) Legacy.

Fig. 9. - The six steps to develop a Citizen Science project in schools⁴⁵

Each phase is crucial: this is why we provide here a list of “guiding questions for teachers” that teachers can tick, ensuring that phase has been completed in the right way. Figures below are therefore a package of implementing- guiding lines for teachers.

44. Adapted from *Citizen Science in the Classroom: A toolkit*, an online course on <https://moodle.eu-citizen.science/course/view.php?id=35>

45. Adapted from *Citizen Science in the Classroom: A toolkit*, an online course on <https://moodle.eu-citizen.science/course/view.php?id=35>

1. DEFINITION OF SCOPE

The first step is to develop an understanding of the issue. This is a collaborative process that informs and guides student actions, helping to build a shared position on an issue. It involves searching for information from various sources (i.e. books, the internet and direct observation).

To focus on the
DRIVING
QUESTION

It depends on how deeply the organization team wants to go into the issues

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- How will the entire process of the project be organized? (i.e. number of teams in the classroom, distribution of the work)
- Which is the issue of my interest or researcher's interest?
- Are there any similar projects?
- What data is needed to answer the driving questions?

WHO?

Teachers

Research team

Fig. 10 - Phase 1 of Citizen Science at school

2. PLANNING

The decisions made at this stage will affect the type of sensing conducted, the kinds of data collected, their accuracy and reliability. It is essential that students are prepared for the tasks to encourage better engagement and stronger feelings of empowerment.

To prepare students for data collection, interpretation and resulting action

Until you feel that students have the necessary skills and understanding to get the most out of the process of citizen sensing

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- What kind of tools or methods do I need to develop my project?
- What kind of data collection do I have to choose?
- Where will the core team collect the suitable data for subsequent analysis?
- Do I have all the devices needed?
- Do they need to be calibrated on students' capabilities?

WHO?

Teachers

PROJECT

Researchers

Fig. 11 - Phase 2 of Citizen Science at school

3. DATA COLLECTION

In this phase students collect data, but how this data is collected and feedback to the participants depends on the technology available: devices or mobile apps. Researchers should supervise students as they collect data and assist with any technology issues.

To gather information to answer the driving question

It depends on the goals and how these goals have informed your planning choices

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- Are we using our devices properly?
- Are there any changes that have to be made, according to researcher feedback?
- Do I have any changes to suggest to researchers because of difficulties students are facing in data collection?

WHO?

Researchers

Students

Fig. 12 - Phase 3 of Citizen Science at school

4. AWARENESS

An important point to analyse is how the students think about and understand the data they have collected. Students should perform these data analyses and use interpretation skills.

To understand the impacts of data and identify opportunities for change and action

Once students feel they understand what the data mean, the group can move on to thinking about potential areas for action

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- How can I improve student understanding of data collected?
- How can data be visualized in an easy-to-understand format?
- Are students aware of what they collected and the impact of their actions in the project?
- May students have suggestions on how to visualize better data?

WHO?

Students guided by the core team

Fig. 13 - Phase 4 of Citizen Science at school

5. REFLECTIONS

If more activities are planned in the future, it is essential to understand what worked well and what could be improved. It is a moment of active participation to criticize activities.

To look back and improve

Planning a gathering to celebrate what has been accomplished during the project can help providing a sort of closure

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- Which is student feedback about the experience?
- Were students able to use devices provided? Or were the proposed data difficult to collect?
- Did the core team need to make the planning phase last longer?
- How have student knowledge and feelings changed over the course of the project?

WHO?

Everyone involved, in particular students

Fig. 14 - Phase 5 of Citizen Science at school

5.a Reflections *in theory*

This stage can be represented with Double Diamond design process.

The figure is based on Design Council's Double Diamond.

Arrows stands for reflection phase that is throughout the process

Fig. 15 - Double Diamond design process

5.b Reflections *in practice*

A helpful way to turn this phase into a moment of collective discussion is to print a table in A3 format with questions that support the evaluation of the activities.

Decisions about the applications can then be made collaboratively through the combined expertise of researchers and teachers.

Once the questions to be asked to the class have been defined, students individually or in groups can express their ideas by providing answers by writing them on sticky notes.

Fig. 16 - First example of an application

5.c Reflections *in practice*

Dotmocracy (also known as points voting) is a method that uses stickers or markers dots to conduct a vote. Researchers and teachers define a set of options to be evaluated (e.g. preference for a title, choice of an image, removal of an activity, etc.).

Each student receives a fixed number of stickers and is asked to place their dots next to beside the options they prefer. The options with the most points at the end of the vote are considered the winners.

Fig. 17 - Second example of an application

6. LEGACY

The kinds of choices made here will affect the impact of the work, and how far-reaching that impact will be.

To realise and sustain this impact, the focus should be on disseminating the findings and advocating for change.

To promote a long team impact of the project

This stage can last as long as the members want to work on having an impact

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- How can I help to disseminate the project?
- Are there any friends, teachers, researchers I am willing to reach out to tell about the project?
- Are there any newspapers or other forms of publishing thanks to whom I can disseminate the project?
- How can I make tools use available for others?

WHO?

All individuals

Fig. 18 - Phase 6 of Citizen Science at school

Conclusion and some tips

Citizen Science projects are based on a teaching/learning model that provides participants with all the tools, **both conceptual and material**, they need to correctly interpret the reality around them through the scientific method, which is, by its very nature, highly structured and based on data and evidence. This in turn will help students forming a skill, **critical thinking**, applicable then to any life or work context ⁴⁶. Indeed, critical thinking is especially important in this day and age considering the onslaught of information and disinformation from various sources, including social media.

46. Caruso, J.P., Israel, N., Rowland, K., Lovelace, M.J., Saunders, M.J. (2016). Citizen science: The small world initiative improved lecture grades and California critical thinking skills test scores of nonscience major students at Florida Atlantic University. *Journal of microbiology, biology education* 17(1): 156-162.

3

Final tips

How to implement a Citizen Science project in your school

1 Don't assume that a citizen science project should be initiated by research experts: schools themselves can propose a project or a series of guiding questions. Schools are encouraged to seek out stakeholders who can support these ideas and provide operational expertise if necessary, creating a collaborative framework around their needs or goals

The European Citizen Science Platform <https://citizenscience.eu/> is an excellent resource for project ideas and inspiration, as well as a source for finding existing Citizen Science projects that schools can join.

2

3 If you come across a Citizen Science project in a school and wish to replicate it, feel free to customize the project to arrange it to your unique context, adapting it to your own school curriculum. Projects often evolve during implementation, influenced by a number of factors, some of which can be unforeseen

Fig. 19 - Final tips to implement a Citizen Science project in the school

A slide deck for teachers

The second part of this toolkit contains an open access **slide deck**, which can be used in different peer-to-peer lessons among teachers to facilitate the realization of existing and novel Citizen Science projects in an accessible and interactive manner.

This deck, together with the Pupil Science Toolbox, will have continued relevance and value for the project's impact sustainability. Schools, even when the MEET project is concluded, will still have access to these materials, freely available on Zenodo, both in English and in Italian. The material can be accessed at the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18433236>

